

alcohols. The unconsumed DCT was estimated by adding 10 ml of 20% KI and titrating the liberated iodine against standard sodium thiosulphate using starch as internal indicator. A blank titration was run with the same volume of DCT.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry of the oxidation of alcohols with DCT can be represented by equations (1) and (2).

The presence of crotyl and cinnamyl aldehydes in the reaction mixture was shown by spot tests⁹. Further, the aldehydes were isolated as their 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone¹⁰ (M.P. 189° and 253° respectively for the hydrazones of crotyl and cinnamyl aldehydes). The sulphonamide was identified by TLC technique¹¹. The solvent was a mixture of chloroform, ethanol and heptane (1 : 1 : 1 by volume) and *p*-dimethyl amino benzaldehyde in 2 N HCl was used as the spray reagent ($R_F=0.93$).

Some typical results of analyses are given in Table 2. The maximum deviation observed in

TABLE 2—ESTIMATION OF CROTYL AND CINNAMYL ALCOHOLS WITH DICHLORAMINE-T

Crotyl alcohol			Cinnamyl alcohol		
Compound taken mg	Compound found mg	Per cent. deviation	Compound taken mg	Compound found mg	Per cent. deviation
6.03	6.05	+0.33	2.20	2.21	+0.45
9.05	9.07	+0.22	4.50	4.53	+0.67
12.05	12.06	+0.083	6.70	6.72	+0.30
15.08	15.10	+0.13	8.90	8.93	+0.34
18.10	18.13	+0.17	11.10	11.15	+0.45
24.20	24.30	+0.41	13.40	13.45	+0.37
30.10	29.90	-0.66	17.80	17.88	+0.45
36.10	35.90	-0.55	22.30	22.40	+0.45

recovery is about 0.7%. The effect of water on the stoichiometry of oxidation of alcohols by DCT was studied. While it had little influence on the oxidation of crotyl alcohol by DCT, recoveries of cinnamyl alcohol were 3% higher when water is present above 8% in the reaction mixture. The presence of neutral compounds on the rate of oxidation of alcohols by DCT was investigated. It was seen that KCN, KCNS, NaCl (~ 0.94 m mole), KBr and KI interfere in the estimation, while Na_2HPO_4 and ZnSO_4 had no influence.

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References

1. T. J. JACOB and C. G. R. NAIR, *Talanta*, 1972, **19**, 347.
2. C. G. R. NAIR and V. R. NAIR, *Talanta*, 1973, **20**, 696.
3. C. G. R. NAIR and P. INDRASENAN, *Talanta*, 1976, **23**, 239.
4. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and M. MADAIHAH, *Curr. Sci.*, 1973, **42**, 420.
5. N. M. MADE GOWDA, A. S. A. MURTHY and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, **44**, 5; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 705.
6. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and B. T. GOWDA, *Talanta*, 1976, **23**, 601.
7. N. M. MADE GOWDA and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, **44**, 757.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "Elementary Practical Organic Chemistry", Part III, Longmans, London, 1958, p. 679.
9. F. FRIGL, "Spot Tests in Organic Analysis", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1956, p. 224.
10. N. D. CHERONIS, J. B. ENTRIKIN and E. M. HODNETT, "Semi-Micro Qualitative Organic Analysis", Interscience, New York, 1965, p. 728.
11. J. M. BOBBITT, A. E. SCHWARTING and R. J. GRITTER, "Introduction to Chromatography", Reinhold, New York, 1968, p. 32.

Study of Essential Oil of *Cymbopogon nardus* var. *stracheyi*

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CYMBOPOGON nardus var. *stracheyi* (N. O. Graminae), a medicinal-aromatic species, possesses high content of the essential oil. The oil has been found to possess antibacterial and anti-fungal properties¹. Orange coloured essential oil from the fresh plant material was extracted by water-steam distillation in 0.25% yield. The physico-chemical properties determined by usual methods² were: specific gravity = 0.8924/20°, refractive index = 1.4824/20°, specific rotation = +2°/20°, acid value = 0.68, ester value = 18.75, ester value after acetylation = 98.39 and carbonyl value as $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$ (oximation, potentiometry) = 8.2.

The oil (100 ml) was fractionated into its constituents employing (i) fractional distillation under reduced pressure (3-4 mm), (ii) column chromatography—using neutral alumina as adsorbent and petroleum ether, *n*-hexane, cyclohexane, benzene, ether, ethyl acetate as eluents. The purity of each fraction was ascertained by thin-layer chromatography and gas-liquid chromatography. In all ten pure fractions were obtained which were identified by preparing their characteristic derivatives and comparing their properties to those mentioned in literature³. The presence of β -pinene, 1-limonene,

methyl heptenone, *d*- α -phellandrene, *d*-citronellal, linalool, citronellol, nerol, geraniol and geranyl acetate was established.

The I.R. spectra and co-TLC of the fractions also confirmed the above results. The alcohols were confirmed by the TLC of their 3,5-dinitrobenzoates over Silica Gel G coated glass plates using different solvent systems and anisaldehyde-H₂SO₄ as spray reagent. The R_F values (using butter yellow as a reference compound) in benzene-petroleum ether (1:1) were observed to be 1.6, 1.3, 1.2 corresponding to citronellol, nerol and geraniol respectively.

Fig. 1.

Chromatogram : Oil of *Cymbopogon nardus*
var : stracheyi

Conditions—

Column—10% Carbowax 20 m
Column temp.—180°C
Carrier gas—Hydrogen (40 ml/min)
Chart speed—0.25 inch/min.

Gas-liquid Chromatography : The GLC of the oil was carried out in a gas chromatograph model—Honeywell HP 7620A equipped with thermal conductivity detector and Carbowax 20M, 10% (18 ft.) column. The column and injection port temperatures were maintained at 180° and 200° respectively, and hydrogen (40 ml/min.) was used as carrier gas. The eleven peaks obtained in the chromatogram were identified by comparing their retention and relative retention times to those of the authentic samples recorded under identical operating conditions. The percentage of each constituent in the oil was determined by calculating corresponding peak area by height $\times$ width at half height method. The results are summarised in Table 1.

Thus, the GLC revealed the presence of one more constituent, i.e., camphene in addition to those identified by chemical methods.

TABLE 1—GLC OF ESSENTIAL OIL OF *C. nardus* VAR. stracheyi

Peak No.	Retention time (minutes)	Percentage in the oil	Compound
1	1.3	0.25	camphene
2	1.5	15.0	β -pinene
3	2.0	28.0	limonene
4	2.5	16.25	α -phellandrene
5	3.0	3.0	methyl heptenone
6	4.6	5.5	citronellal
7	5.6	8.0	linalool
8	12.6	6.0	citronellol
9	12.7	7.0	geranyl acetate
10	14.8	3.0	nerol
11	16.2	8.0	geraniol

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References

1. C. S. MATHELA and G. K. SINHA. *Planta Medica* (communicated).
2. E. GUENTHER, "The Essential Oils", Vol. I, D. Van Nostrand Co., New York, 1955.
3. E. GUENTHER, "The Essential Oils", Vol. II, D. Van Nostrand Co., New York, 1949.

Colouring Matters from the Flowers of *Thunbergia laurifolia*

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THE plant *Thunbergia laurifolia* (N. O. Acanthaceae) is a large climber and is found throughout India¹. The flowers, light blue in colour with yellowish throat, on chemical examination yielded Delphinidin 3 : 5-di-*o*- β -D-glucopyranoside, apigenin and apigenin-7-*o*- β -D-glucopyranoside.

The fresh flowers were extracted with 1% methanolic hydrochloric acid and the extract after concentration under reduced pressure was extracted with ether. The violet red solution gave compound A and the dried ether extract on crystallisation from acetone : methanol (1 : 1) gave compound B. The extracted flowers were air-dried and refluxed with ethanol for 10 hr. The concentrated extract on crystallisation from methanol : benzene (1 : 1) gave compound C.

Compound A (*anthocyanin*) ; violet-red ; hygroscopic ; $\lambda_{\max}$ 535 nm, shift in AlCl₃ (25 nm). Hydrolysis with 20% CH₃OH-HCl gave anthocyanidin and a sugar identified to be D-glucose. The antho-